

Notes on Disjunctive Antecedents in Conditionals
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Let me consider the case of disjunction in the antecedent:¹

- (1) a. If I had struck this match and it had been dry or wet, it would have lit.
- b. If I had struck this match, it would have lit.

Assume the contextual domain contains only worlds in which the match is dry, but worlds in which I strike it and worlds in which I don't. Then, the antecedents in (1a&b), which are after all equivalent, will both be compatible with the contextual domain. So, there would be no need for context change in either case. The context-dynamic account, as developed here, seems just as clueless about the apparent non-equivalence of these two conditionals as the static semantic account. But I presented (1) earlier as *prima facie* evidence that the context is easily shifted. It now seems that it shifts even more easily than predicted by my own account. What to do? I will discuss two options: one cautiously appeals to pragmatics, the other tries to tie things down technically. Let me sketch the technical option first.²

An auxiliary hypothesis is needed. A disjunction *p or q* is only felicitous if the context is compatible with both *p* and *q*. See Grice (1989) and Vainikka (1987) for relevant discussion.³ We could amend the felicity conditions for conditionals as follows:

- (2) $\forall$ (*if p*) (*q*) is felicitous at *w* wrt ϕ, g only if
 - (i) $\llbracket p \rrbracket^{\phi, g} \in \phi$, and
 - (ii) *p* is felicitous at *w* wrt $D(\phi, g, w)$

The idea is this: normally a disjunction is only felicitous if for all the speaker knows either disjunct may be true. When a disjunction is embedded, felicity is evaluated with

¹Disjunctions in conditional antecedents are a well-known problem (Fine 1975 ; Nute 1975, 1980; Loewer 1976; Ellis, Jackson, and Paragetter 1977; McKay and Inwagen 1977; Warmbrod 1981a). See Nute (1984: Section 7, pp. 413-418) for a summary discussion.

²Either of these approaches seem preferable to any brute-force LF transformation from *if p or q, then r* to (*if p, r*) and (*if q, r*). Such attempts are known by the term "translation lore" in the philosophical literature.

³There are other problems with disjunction in modal contexts, specifically the observation that disjunction under a (deontic) possibility modal has an unexpectedly strong reading. I am not sure what the connection is to the problem I treat here. Relevant work on the interaction of disjunction and modality includes (Ross 1941; Kamp 1973, 1979; Higginbotham 1991).

respect to the local context introduced by the conditional operator. In effect, we behave as if $D(w)$ were the context for an assertion of the disjunction. In Stalnaker's term, $D(w)$ is a "derived" context. The idea then is that this felicity condition may drive domain expansion as well. Both disjuncts need to be represented in the contextual domain.

→ Unfortunately, while the account now correctly predicts that (1a) expresses a stronger claim than (1b), it arguably makes wrong predictions as well. McKay and Van Inwagen (1977) present the following examples:

- (3) a. If Spain had fought on either the Allied side or the Nazi side, it would have fought on the Nazi side.
- b. Therefore, if Spain had fought on the Allied side, it would have fought on the Nazi side.

The suggestion is that since (3b) is obviously false and (3a) is arguably true, we cannot accept the inference from *if p or q, r* to *if p, r*.

My impression is that (3a) is in fact very odd (because it is essentially self-contradictory). Compare it to what I find a much more normal way of expressing what (3a) tries to express:

- (4) If Spain had fought on one of the sides in the war, it would have fought on the Nazi side.

Irene Heim (class notes) has the following examples that show the same effect:

- (5) a. If I had called one of my sisters, I would have called Josefine.
b. If I had called Hildegard, Josefine, or Martina, I would have called Josefine.

Assuming that the speaker has three sisters (Hildegard, Josefine, and Martina), the two sentences in (5) should be equivalent. But (5b) is far stranger than (5a).

Using an explicit disjunction in the antecedent seems to quite reliably trigger the addition of both possibilities to the realm of possibilities. Forms of expressions that "hide" the disjunctive force do not do so. These are very interesting facts, which I won't be able to discuss any further here. If my attempt at dismissing McKay and van Inwagen's counterexample is deemed to be unsatisfactory, then we have to move to a more cautious

way of explaining why the two conditionals in (1) are felt to be non-equivalent. If we have to take (3a) as wellformed and sensible, then we should not enforce that (1a) is asserted only in contexts where worlds answering to both disjuncts are represented in the domain. We could still say that nevertheless (1a), when encountered in a context with no further clues as to what the intended realm of possibilities is, is naturally taken to presuppose a context where both disjuncts are represented in the contextual domain. Even this cautious way of putting the point is preferable to the problems that the static standard account has with disjunctive antecedents.

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